

Ethical and philosophical issues of operating of functional objects; a developing approach

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The major problem with functional objects is that the objects themselves have the capacity to work. Because of this inherent ability there are at present two common views as to the best way of caring for them.

Ethically we need to consider function as one of the significant material attributes of an object that needs to be conserved. We should not class operation as a deterioration agent but as an option available for interpretation of the object through the "storage and occasional use scenario". Function needs to be included in the significance assessment process.

Museums need to invest a little in the development of maintenance and storage materials and approaches for functional objects to ensure our engineering heritage is conserved appropriately. With this work we can forge a "middle way" between the two extreme approaches and adopt more maintenance and occasional use based strategies.

The ability to operate and function is an intrinsic property of technology objects which many conservators would rather ignore! Life seems safer that way.

When writing this paper I dragged through (English) literature searches and my electronic records of papers (published and unpublished) from the mid 80's to today (2007) and it amazes me that the ground has changed so little.

We still see the "conservation vs restoration" debate and the "use verses non use" saga.

We still seem unable to see the logic of the "middle way". Bob Barclay's wonderful book on the conservation of Musical instruments is a template for the way we should be going with technology objects conservation.

I will quickly pull some points from the literature then outline my own approaches to operation of Functional Objects. It is interesting to note my views have changed somewhat as the type of objects I treat have changed and risks have diminished.

In 1984 I stated;

"The major problem with functional objects is that the objects themselves have the capacity to work. Because of this inherent ability there are at present two common views as to the best way of caring for them.

The dilemma appears to be between use and non use of the object.

Just the fact that a object has been put into a museum is often used as a rationale for either its use or non use. Little account is taken of how these affect its long term survival as a piece of useful cultural material.

In the first view use and wear are assumed to be directly linked. Wear aligned with uncontrolled degradation. Hence the object cannot be used.

Most museums fall into this trap.

The second view is often equally as simplistic in assuming that the object was designed to work hence it would be somehow unethical if it were not to do so even when long past its economic life. Hence the object is kept working even if this means it loses most of its original parts and heads towards a replica.

An example of this philosophy is the Shuttleworth Collection in England. Vehicles, motor cycles and 26 flying aircraft.

Running concurrent with that second view is the "Concourse" (or oldtimer) method whereby all machines are restored to a pristine "original condition" that never existed when the object was originally made or used."

Of course neither view is really sustainable."

Ethics, integrity and significance of the artefact

Significance is a difficult term to define in a museum context. What makes something worthy of preservation for the greater good of humanity? What about it warrants the expenditure of storage and conservation resources that attempt to prolong its presence as a community resource? Defining significance, the reason why an object is being kept in the collection, has pivotal importance to designing a conservation plan for an objects ongoing care. Without defining the objects significance questions such as it's potential uses in a museum cannot be answered.

Kuhn , argues that it is the "historical integrity" of the object that we are preserving in museums "Time leaves marks of a different kind on an artefact ... natural aging ... signs of past use and abuse ... traces that time has left on an artefact must not be altered- much less removed - ... loss of such evidence of past use and age also entails an inevitable loss of historical significance."

This theme is common of the "scientific conservation" approach - nothing is more important than historical integrity of the object, it provides a historical document, or primary source for interpretation of the objects significance.

Others argue that the conservation ethic approach of focusing on retaining material evidence is schizoid and should be abandoned for a new approach that has a primary objective of 'exploitation our artefacts for the public benefit'.

This kind of argument was further explored in the "Aircraft to Artefact: Exploring the principles of Historic Preservation" and "Risks and Rewards: Perspective's on operating Mechanical Artefacts" and it seems that we have got a more rational series of approaches over the last 10 years. Many of these are outlined in the papers of Wain, Hallam and Thurrowgood in "Bigstuff 04" and in Bob Barclay's wonderful book. Risk, Significance, Maintenance, Sustainability and Planning are all part of functional objects conservation.

Non-operation

Gillespie argues in "Aircraft to Artefact: Exploring the principles of Historic Preservation" that the risk of operating historic aircraft is too great due to the skills required and the outcome of mechanical failure. Most aircraft fall out of the sky if the engines stop or crash if pilot skill is not up to scratch.

Schlichting argues in "Risks and Rewards: Perspective's on operating Mechanical Artefacts" that important information is being lost by restoring objects to operate rather than preserving and conserving them. Initially he seems to be against all operation but this is not the case. He states "I see two distinct components in preserving and interpreting our industrial heritage. The first preserving the technology, and the second is preserving the evidence of the human component. We preserve technology by emphasising the function, the materials, the motion, the knowledge and skills, which is best done with a fully functioning accurate machine. On the other hand, we preserve evidence of the human component by doing all we can to conserve, intact, both physical and non physical remains of the object and its associated materials.

These two tasks are the root of the museums mandate, and cannot be done using the same artefact." He also tries to dispel the "myth" that use preserves, but fails in my opinion as he draws on no solid data only generalisations.

Barclay on the other hand points to the undocumented work of "silent artisans" as a reason for the remarkable preservative qualities of use.

Ferrel in "Risks and Rewards" argues for preservation and interpretation as opposed to restoration and function. "Documents be they inscriptions on paper or three dimensional objects like steam locomotives, can be read. Each has a story to tell. And if a document is altered or corrupted its value as a source of information is compromised or destroyed"

He fails to recognise and address the added information that function adds to the object. I have argued similarly about the documentary nature of objects but have not used this as an argument for non-use. I now argue that we need to assess the significance of form and function to the story the museum wishes the object to tell.

This is best demonstrated in the National Museum of Australia (NMA) by the museums approach to the conservation of a 1860's Landau. We decided form (particularly the original surfaces) was deemed most significant so the coach now sits on a storage display trolley never to move on its wheels again behind a horse. (photo 1). Form is being conserved but the functional side of the story is being lost.

(photo 1)

Operation and occasional use.

Little scientific work has been done by museums or collection institutions on the affects of use and periodic maintenance on objects long term storage. This is amazing when we consider how much work has been done on the effects of light and relative humidity on objects in museums used in exhibitions. Many authors in the "Risks and Rewards" argue that use is an appropriate museum activity. Many authors in this group discuss the risk of objects in storage or the degradation resulting from lack of care in storage and use this as an argument for use. Again much debate has been put forward as to whether the preservation or restoration approach is appropriate and should be incorporated in the operation of an object. Hence it has become a debate about restoration not running operation. Many of the supporters of operation do not see any worth in "original fabric of an object". To quote John Chapman "paint is a consumable item." I doubt he would say the same about a painting! Little discussion is encountered on maintenance and monitoring programs except for Mann and more recently Wain, Hallam and Paine. The connection between a sustainable maintenance program for a operational object and it's preservation seems to be missing in many museums.

The NMA has a Murray River Paddle Steamer the Enterprise (photo 2). It's function is deemed most significant, as are the skills of the engineers, through a volunteer program both are conserved. Surfaces and parts are replaced as required leading to a diminution of the original materials. The vessel is maintained in "continuance" (Barclay). Function is conserved. Skills are preserved. Original material is lost.

(photo 2)

Conversely the NMA has the Smith quartet, stringed instruments made by an Australian luthier. These instruments are played under a regiment of "exhibition/storage and occasional use" which allows us to conserve both form and function.

Wear

Wear is the main argument that is used to stop the operation of objects. I feel this is incorrect. Although wear analysis is done by WA Museum on a small scale no mention of it as a monitoring technique is made in the museum literature. It is a common industrial technique for ensuring that risks are minimised and catastrophic failure is avoided. By tracking wear the objects progress through its economic life can be plotted and failure avoided. Thurrowgood and Hallam have expanded on this with the concepts of "economic life" and "Just Noticeable Wear". We have found at the NMA that un-maintained, unplanned, intermittent operation gives us the maximum wear rates thru promotion of corrosive wear. We have also found that through use of appropriate maintenance, inhibition systems, oils lubricants and coatings that wear can be reduced to negligible levels.

Maintenance

Many papers have been published that discuss the problems of the storage of functional objects in a military context for periods of non operation. Dehumidification and periodic exercise are necessary to maintain functional objects in operable condition in long term storage. David Monthan Air Force Base (USA) uses natural dehumidification and yearly maintenance on its flying aircraft. Some aircraft have been stored for 20 years prior to being flown. Maintenance has always been recognised as being important to maintain operating functional objects in safe condition. The consequences of incorrect storage have been long known. Weil, among others, has recognised the need for conservation treatments to be based on sound maintenance to achieve the desired affect. Hallam and Ashton have out line the need for a maintenance and monitoring approach to the conservation of functional objects and that some objects may be in a operable condition to allow for conservation maintenance.

I believe that maintenance is the most cost effective way of looking after Functional Objects, even if that maintenance is just ensuring the objects is cleaned regularly, appropriately supported and stored. As the amount of use increases so to does the maintenance load. Eventually an organisation will find the load unsustainable. The trick is to ensure the operation of objects does not lead to cutting maintenance below an optimal level. This is one area in which museums need to do more work on appropriate maintenance programs for storage and use of objects.

A Middle Way

I believe that function is one of the criteria that museums and collecting institutions must consider when storing or using a functional object.

If we conserve a functional object without considering the roll of function we have not done our job properly. Form and function both need to be conserved. We need to consider the significance of both to appropriate engineering cultures.

Technically we have a trade-off – a sliding scale of what we consider important – form or function. If we decide form is most significant then our treatment will compromise function. Function is inhibited.

If function is significant then extensive use will lead to form being compromised.

I believe we can conserve both form and function if we follow Barkley's "exhibition (storage) and limited use" scenario. The NMA has done this with a variety of restored and original motor vehicles. The best example is the Bean car which Frances Birtles drove from London to Sydney in 1927. Functionality and original materials were all conserved. (photo 3). Appropriate inhibition materials and a sustainable maintenance programs, which may include running or "rotating", make the conservation of form and function possible. We have taken a similar approach with an original unrestored Outside Broadcast TV van. The van is drivable and TV channel still operates. Form and function are conserved.

(photo 3)

Wrap-up

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